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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this paper, we explore the use of a novel spiral phase plate (SPP) for the imaging of biological samples in cryogenic transmission electron microscopy. The SPP adds an angularly dependent phase shift $e^{il\Phi_k}$ in reciprocal space and is used to enhance edge contrast. Simulations show that phase contrast is enhanced with an $l = 1$ SPP that is positioned at the back focal plane of the electron microscope. We experimentally validated simulation results by introducing a Si₃N₄ thin film SPP in a 200kV Arctica cryo-EM in Maastricht and imaging protein molecules with it under cryogenic conditions. It is shown that a SPP can strongly enhance the phase contrast at near and slight underfocus conditions.

The spiral phase plate works as a physical edge enhancer for weak phase objects. This is already a crude but robust form of sparse sampling which correlates to the result of the T3.1. The application of the SPP is also a proof of concept that orbital angular momentum can help for the direct identification of individual proteins which is consistent with the target of WP5. Moreover, the test of SPP offers a guidance for the tests of the Quantum sorter in T5.3 and T5.4. It also gives us more possibilities in performing T5.3 as we could integrate a SPP with a Quantum sorter for the identification of individual proteins at certain orientations.

SPIRAL PHASE CONTRAST IMAGING OF PROTEINS IN CRYO-ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

Frozen-hydrated biological samples are mainly composed of light elements which result in very low amplitude contrast and weak phase changes of the electron beam in cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM). Traditionally, images are obtained at under focus to obtain phase contrast. Analogous to light microscopy, devices commonly referred to as “phase plates” have been developed to provide in-focus phase contrast. They can also boost the low-resolution components of images collected at slight under focus. Here, we study the influence of the spiral phase plate (SPP) on the image formation model in cryo-EM by adding a phase-change $e^{il\Phi_k}$ which is angularly dependent to the exit wave in the Fourier space. The SPP can produce images with enhanced edge contrast, therefore better contrast at the sample borders. The results are compared with images without SPP under different foci showing that SPP strongly enhance the phase contrast. The effect of misalignments has been investigated. A SPP was introduced in a cryo-EM and preliminary data were collected, corroborating simulation results.

INTRODUCTION

Cryo-EM has become a powerful tool for structural biologists to study structure-function relationships of their protein of interest. Unlike macromolecular crystallography (MX), cryo-EM allows to visualize complexes at multiple conformations simultaneously; these conformations can be sorted out computationally afterwards. Not seldom, samples are not only structurally but also compositionally heterogeneous. For macromolecular compounds that are too small or too heterogeneous, single particle reconstruction (SPA) schemes will fail. In fact, there is a large discrepancy between the rapidly increasing number of cryo-electron microscopes installed worldwide and their SPA potential versus the actual number of cryo-EM structures deposited within the protein data bank (PDB). Ultimately, one wish to have an optimal image of each particle individually, as each particle itself will define one point within the multidimensional conformation space a protein can adapt.

Phase plates have been used to increase, in particular, the low resolution components in cryo-EM data. Conventionally (cTEM), data are recorded at slight underfocus, to introduce phase contrast. The contrast transfer function is an oscillating function that describes the amount of information at each spatial frequency Fourier space. Close to focus, in cTEM, there is no to very little transfer of information of the low resolution term. When moving further out of focus, the amount of information transfer at low resolution will increase, at the costs of i) introducing more oscillations of the CTF where the contrast is inverted, and ii) increased damping of the higher resolution terms due to envelop functions of the microscope. Using a phase plate, an additional phase shift is introduced between the unscattered and the scattered electron beam, providing phase contrast at low resolution even at close-to-Scherzer focus. Phase plates that have so far been used for cryo-EM, include a Zernike and Volta phase plate [1]. The latter became commercially available a few years ago, and was shown to yield advantages for the solution of very small proteins. The Volta phase plate (VPP) is relatively simple in usage, as the volta potential can be created at any position of the back focal plane. However, it also has disadvantages, such as the lack of constant phase shift and the damping of high resolution terms.

In here, we introduce a new type of phase plate, a Spiral Phase Plate (SPP). It introduces an angularly dependent phase shift in the back focal plane of the microscope. We present simulations on how proteins would look like when imaged with such SPP, demonstrate an actual implementation, and discussed the prospects of phase plates for structural cellular biology.

THEORY

Image formation of biological samples in cryo-EM can be modelled using the specimen's scattering properties, the influence of optics and the detector response [2]. We calculated the specimen interaction potential using the isolated atom superposition approximation (IASA) which also takes account the solvent, ions and molecular interactions. A multislice algorithm was used to calculate the electron propagation through the specimen with the slice thickness at 1 nm [3]. The difference between the signal and noise transferring was included via the detective quantum efficiency.

The interaction potential is separated into two parts: inelastic contributions and elastic contributions where the inelastic scattering contributes to the amplitude contrast and elastic scattering contributes to the phase contrast. The total interaction potential can be written as:

$$v_{tot}^{int}(\mathbf{r}) = (v_{atom}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{bond}(\mathbf{r})) + iv_{ab} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$ is the position of the electron wave. The elastic scattering includes 'atom' contributions ($v_{atom}(\mathbf{r})$) and 'bond' contributions ($v_{bond}(\mathbf{r})$). We calculated the interaction of the incident electrons with the specimen atoms based on IASA method and it contributes to the dominant part of the interaction potential [2]. The 'bond' contributions consist of the influence of solvent, ions and molecular interactions. Inelastic scattering, v_{ab} , was calculated as the imaginary part in the model and it consisted of the interaction of the incident electrons with free electrons in specimen ($\Delta E \sim 20 eV$) and atom cores ($\Delta E > 100 eV$).

The multislice approach take the specimen thickness and multiple scattering into consideration [3]. An incident plane wave has its function as $\Psi_0(x, y) = 1$, propagates though the n slice with the slice thickness Δz and leave the specimen with the wave function $\Psi_{exit}(x, y)$. In our simulation, the specimen slice thickness is 1 nm. The probability of multiple scattering events is less than 5% and therefore, the weak phase object approximation is valid [4]. All the microscope aberrations, defocus and electron source temporal coherence are included in phase dependent contrast transfer function (CTF). In our simulation, the spiral phase plate was incorporated by introducing an angularly dependent phase changes $e^{il\phi_k}$ to the electron wave in reciprocal space resulting in the wave function $\Psi(k) = \Psi_{exit}(k)e^{il\phi_k}$ [5][6]. Here, l is the topological charge of the electron beam, and ϕ_k is the angular coordinate. When $l = 1$, the value we used here, the phase angularly change from $-\pi$ to π and it produces a spiral shape phase contrast transfer function [7].

The electron intensity in the image plane ($I_0(x, y)$) can be obtained by: 1. multiply the Fourier transform of the exitwave $\Psi_{exit}(x, y)$ and CTF, 2. inverse Fourier transform of the product in previous step and square. The intensity is:

$$I_0(x, y) = |\mathcal{F}^{-1}[\mathcal{F}[\Psi_{exit}(x, y)] \text{CTF}]|^2 \quad (2)$$

Contributions to the detector response in our simulation include conversion factor (CF), modulation transfer function (MTF) and detective quantum efficiency (DQE). The MTF is the Fourier transform of the point spread function (PSF) which blurs the image as a function of spatial frequency. The DQE is square of the ratio of MTF and NTF, where NTF is the noise

transfer function. The readout noise and dark current were also calculated in this simulation. The final detected electron intensity, I , on detector is [2]:

$$I(x, y) = I_{rn} + I_{dc} + CF \cdot \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\mathcal{F}[P_{oiss}(\Phi_e \cdot \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\tilde{I}_0(q)\sqrt{DQE(q)})] \cdot NTF(q)] \quad (3)$$

Where I_{rn} is the readout current and I_{dc} is the dark current. CF is the conversion factor of the detector, in [ADU/e⁻]. P_{oiss} is the Poisson distribution that weights the probability of arrival of an electron for a given dose and expected intensity.

RESULTS

By changing the defocus value, we studied the image contrast of the human H chain ferritin, with and without SPP. The effect of defocus is validated experimentally on a carbon film cross grating which is used for calibration. The experimental data were acquired on a 200kV Arctica cryo-EM with a purposely built spiral phase plate inserted in the objective holder position. The SPP had been shaped using focus ion beam (FIB) milling of a Si_3N_4 film. We also present the effect of misalignment in modelling and the comparison is made between the modelled images and the experiment data.

For biological specimen, the phase contrast mainly obtained by highly underfocus as it is shown in Figure 1b. Figure 1 shows simulated cryo-EM images of human apo-ferritin. In the absence of a phase plate, phase contrast is obtained by defocusing (Fig 1b, 1 μm underfocus) which provides good low-spatial-frequency information compared to close-to-focus condition (Fig. 1a, 100 nm underfocus).

The simulated images with SPP are shown in Figure 1c and 1d. Fig 1c shows an image close to focus, $\Delta f = 100$ nm. The contrast in this image is much higher than that of the image without SPP (Fig. 1a). Figure 1d shows a simulated image with SPP at the same defocus as was used for Fig 1b (1 μm underfocus). Comparison of these two images shows the edge-enhancement properties of the SPP.

Figure 1. Image of human H-chain ferritin under different defocus values (a) without SPP, $\Delta f = 100$ nm, (b) without SPP, $\Delta f = 1000$ nm, (c) with SPP, $\Delta f = 100$ nm, (d) with SPP, $\Delta f = 1000$ nm. The scale bar corresponds to 5 nm. The acceleration voltage is 200 kV, integrated flux 40 $\text{e}^-/\text{Å}^2$, the detector is Falcon III.

Figure 2 shows the contrast transfer function for the SPP, both in 2D (Fig. 2a) and in 1D (Fig. 2b) at different azimuthal angles. The three different CTF curves plotted in Figure 2b correspond to the lines shown in Figure 2a. For example, the blue line on the right side of the Thon ring illustrates the high contrast at low frequencies, corresponding to the dark area on the right side of Figure 1d. As a consequence, signals with different spatial frequencies can be obtained in the same image at different azimuthal angles indicated by different peaks in Figure 2b. Similar to Hilbert phase plate which has π phase difference between two half-planes of the plate, SPP also has a π phase difference on any two different counter azimuthal angle across the central point,

such as orange line (0) and yellow (π). When the defocus value is $1 \mu\text{m}$, the phase contrast is azimuthally-varying which is indicated by the three different lines in figure 2d. Due to the gradually varying phase contrast at different azimuthal angle, the images shown in Figure 1c and 1d have shadow-like artefacts which is similar to that from the Hilbert phase plate.

We also collected some experimental data with a SPP. Figure 3a is the image of the Si_3N_4 thin film SPP and Figure 3b shows an image collected at a defocus value of close to 100 nm . The defocus value cannot be precisely determined as the spiral Thon ring is not compatible with the current algorithm for defocus calculation. The contrast of protein edges is strongly enhanced with SPP, and it shows an azimuthally-varying phase contrast. However, Figure 3b has a high noise signal, which is due to the inelastic scattering caused by Si_3N_4 . Moreover, the protein particles in Figure 3b have not complete the same contrast as it is shown in Figure 1b, where proteins are more 'light' in experimental image. The reason of contrast difference is mainly due to the misalignment of the SPP with the optical axis.

Figure 2. Thon ring and one-dimensional contrast transfer function (CTF) at different azimuthal angles (a)(b) at 100 nm underfocus and (c)(d) $1 \mu\text{m}$ underfocus with SPP.

Figure 3. (a) The image of SPP with FIB milling Si_3N_4 film, (b) ferritin with SPP, $\Delta f \sim 100$ nm. The scale bar is 30 nm. The acceleration voltage is 200 kV, integrated flux $40 \text{ e}^-/\text{Å}^2$ with Falcon III detector used in integration node.

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of the misalignment of the spiral phase plate on the image contrast. Figure 4b shows the condition when the central beam locates at site 1, the image of protein is 'lighter' compared to the contrast in Figure 1c. When the central beam moves from the site 1 gradually to site 4, the contrast of the protein changes dramatically from 'light' to 'dark'. Only when the central beam is close to the central point of the SPP (Figure 4c and 4d), the particle shows 'topological' characteristic. Figure 4f to 4i exhibit the Thon rings corresponding to Figure 4f to 4e. The phase singularity moves from site 1 to site 4 on shown in Figure 4f to Figure 4i. Although there is not much difference between contrast transfer functions at high spatial frequency, the low spatial frequency part changes. In Figure 4f, the low spatial frequency region has more 'light' (1) than 'dark' (-1), therefore, the particle looks 'light'. When the central beam is close to the central part of the SPP, the low spatial frequency region has about equally 'light' and 'dark' contrast, so that the particle shows shadow-like artefacts (Figure 4c and 4d). When the central locates at site 4, the 'dark' contrast dominates at the low spatial frequency region, and as a consequence, the particle is more dark.

Figure 4. The effect of the misalignment of the SPP. (a) the image of the SPP and four blue dots shows the location of the central electron beam at four different places relative to the SPP, (b)(c)(d)(e) the images of the protein EspB when the central beam at the site 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively, (f)(g)(h)(i) the corresponding thon ring when the the central beam at the site 1, 2, 3 and 4.

DISCUSSION

We investigate the use of a SPP for cryo-EM imaging of weak-phase frozen-hydrated biological macromolecules. Inserting an $l = 1$ SPP at the back focal plane of the electron microscope helps us to get a good phase contrast especially close to in-focus condition (Figure 1). The SPP adds a $e^{il\Phi_k}$ phase shift to the exit wave, resulting in an angularly dependent contrast transfer function and enhanced edge contrast.

However, there are two main difficulties in implementing the SPP in real experiment: defocus value determination and SPP alignment. We study the effect of the defocus on the contrast transfer function as well as the influence on the image. As the real defocus value is calculated via the Fourier transform of the real image, and current algorithm does not fit the spiral Thon ring. The simulated results can help us with defocus calculation. The misalignment of the SPP has a great impact on the contrast of the particles. The reason is that SPP adds an azimuthally-varying phase change to the contrast transfer function, different misaligned direction results in completely different phase contrast especially at low spatial frequency.

The simulation helps us to understand the enhancement of the phase contrast by adding an SPP, as well as the optimization of the data acquisition. The experiment is done with Si_3N_4 SPP, illustrating the potential of SPP for edge enhancement. However, due to the scattering caused by the Si_3N_4 , such phase plate will also introduce undesired scattering and increase noise. To overcome this, we also plan to do further experiments with magnetic or electrostatic phase plate that will have less scattering effects.

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AUTHOR / CONTRIBUTIONS

Y. Zhang and R. B.G. Ravelli performed image simulation; V. Grillo, R. E. Dunin-Borkowski, R. B.G. Ravelli and P.J. Peters designed the experiments; P. Rosi fabricated the spiral phase plate; Y. Zhang, P. Rosi, P.H. Lu, A.H. Tavabi, V. Grillo and R. B.G. Ravelli performed the experiments; Y. Zhang and R. B.G. Ravelli analyzed the data; all of the authors discussed the results and contributed to the text of the manuscript.

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CONCLUSIONS

We describe the application of a SPP in cryo-EM for weak-phase object imaging, especially for frozen-hydrated biological macromolecules. Both simulation and experiment demonstrates that $l = 1$ SPP positioned at the back focal plane can strongly enhance phase contrast. The influence of the defocus value with SPP has been investigated. Some of the experimental difficulties have been discussed in this paper; in particular accurate defocusing and SPP alignments. The effect of SPP misalignments have been illustrated through simulation, which provides a guide for doing better experiments.

Experiments were performed with thin film Si_3N_4 SPP mounted in a 200 kv Artica cryo-EM. Experimental data not seldom revealed SPP misalignments, which we tried to correct for by comparisons with SPP misalignments in simulations. Significant contrast enhancement could be observed in the presence of a SPP. In order to generate a maximum of 2π phase shift by a Si_3N_4 layer on a solid support, a relatively thick SPP needed to be used. This created extra scattering of the electron beam in the back focal plane of the objective lens, diminishing the signal-to-noise contrast within the final image. Thus, the future plan is to do further experiments with electrostatic phase plate without any post sample scattering.

INTERNAL REVIEW

Referee:

Stefano Frabboni, UMR

The work is very interesting and surely worth a publication. It can be the beginning of a more systematic study on the use of these phase plates in cryomicroscopy.

In general however for the final publication I would suggest to add the case of dark field and /or the experimental data with a chopstick.

I indicated a few typos and the need to specify the meaning of the terms in eq.3.

Rebuttal:

Vincenzo Grillo, CNR

Thank you for your feedback.

We integrated some of the suggestions. We will further improve our work in the future.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL